

masses were plugged and placed inside incubators at 8, 12, 15, 17, and 20 °C temperatures for 0, 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, and 21 d.

Four test tubes with egg masses per treatment were exposed at room temperature for embryonic development. The dates on which eggs hatched were recorded. Emerged larvae were counted after 4 d and egg masses were dissected to determine the number of unhatched eggs.

Ten larvae from each egg mass were caged on potted IR36 plants at the booting stage. At 24 d after infestation, the plants were dissected and larvae surviving counted.

During the cool months (Dec-Feb), YSB eggs hatched normally 8 d after oviposition. Handling delayed hatching by 1 d, regardless of incubation temperature (Fig. 1a).

Hatching could be delayed 25 d when eggs were incubated at 15 °C, and 23 d at 17 °C (Fig. 1b). Eggs stored at

Incubation period, egg hatchability, and larval survival of YSB as affected by storage period at different temperature regimes.

8 °C for 3, 6, 10, 15, and 21 d, and at 12 °C for 15 and 21 d did not hatch.

Larval survival decreased drastically with a progressive increase in storage period at low temperatures; it was least

affected when eggs were incubated at 20 °C (Fig. 1c).

For optimum hatchability and larval survival, storage of YSB egg masses should not exceed 10 d at 15 °C. □

Phenolic compounds, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in rice leaves of varieties resistant to rice thrips

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Rice varieties differ in susceptibility to the rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis*. We examined concentrations of phenolic compounds, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in the leaves of seven susceptible and six resistant varieties.

Leaves of 30-d-old healthy and infested rice plants were analyzed, with two replications per analysis. Catechol was the standard for colorimetric assay. Total phenols were separated and

estimated by silica-gel thin-layer chromatography (TLC). Salicylic acid was separated using chloroform:acetic acid (9:1 vol/vol) solvent system. Chlorogenic and gallic acids were separated using methanol:acetic acid:water (9:1:1 vol/vol) solvent system. Co-chromatography with authentic samples indicated that most of the phenols belonged to benzoic and cinnamic acid derivatives.

Resistant varieties possessed significantly higher content of total phenols (Table 1). Salicylic acid was higher in susceptible varieties, but concentrations of chlorogenic and gallic acids were higher in resistant varieties (Table 2). Reducing sugars were significantly higher in susceptible varieties. Free amino acid content was generally higher in susceptible varieties. □

Table 1. Phenols, reducing sugars, and free amino acids in healthy (H) and thrips-infested (I) plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties.

Variety	mg/g fresh weight of leaves					
	Phenols		Reducing sugars		Free amino acids	
	H	I	H	I	H	I
<i>Resistant</i>						
Ptb21	5.45	5.50	4.20	4.60	3.65	4.55
Mozhikaruppu	5.05	4.95	3.55	4.50	2.75	4.45
Kandagasalai	6.35	5.70	3.85	4.53	3.35	4.40
CO 3	5.05	5.45	2.98	3.55	2.95	3.70
TNR1	5.40	5.25	3.13	3.28	2.70	3.30
IR62	4.80	4.55	2.25	2.98	2.95	3.20
Mean	5.35	5.23	3.33	3.90	3.06	3.93
<i>Susceptible</i>						
Bhavani	3.30	3.05	6.03	5.40	3.10	3.95
ADT38	3.80	3.65	7.43	7.88	3.85	4.40
IR26	3.00	2.80	5.13	5.78	2.85	3.75
IR34	3.10	3.05	4.90	5.15	3.90	4.30
IR8	3.05	2.75	5.03	5.28	3.65	4.50
Vani	3.45	3.40	7.40	7.68	3.30	4.10
CO 43	3.45	3.15	6.08	6.35	3.25	4.10
Mean	3.31	3.12	6.00	6.36	3.41	4.16
<i>LSD values</i>						
Healthy vs infested	0.17**		0.36**		0.54**	
Resistant vs susceptible	0.17***		0.36***		0.54*	
Between varieties	0.12**		0.26**		0.39*	

Table 2. Salicylic, chlorogenic, and gallic acids in healthy (H) and thrips-infested (I) plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties.

Variety	mg/g fresh weight of leaves					
	Salicylic ^a		Chlorogenic ^b		Gallic ^b	
	H	I	H	I	H	I
<i>Resistant</i>						
Ptb 21	0.22	0.30	2.40	2.32	0.84	1.16
Mozhikaruppu	0.20	0.33	2.48	2.80	1.20	0.96
Kandagasalai	0.31	0.29	1.92	2.80	1.20	0.60
CO 3	0.30	0.25	2.48	2.48	1.00	1.00
TNRI	0.27	0.28	2.56	1.84	0.96	0.64
IR62	0.31	0.30	2.32	1.84	0.80	0.60
Mean	0.27	0.29	2.36	2.35	1.00	0.83
<i>Susceptible</i>						
Bhavani	0.64	0.60	1.44	1.30	0.40	0.36
IR8	0.76	0.77	1.36	1.34	0.40	0.41
IR26	0.60	0.59	1.44	1.40	0.40	0.38
IR34	0.56	0.57	0.94	1.10	0.38	0.32
ADT38	0.61	0.63	1.48	1.00	0.60	0.50
CO 43	0.55	0.57	1.52	1.60	0.38	0.42
Vani	0.68	0.69	1.04	1.24	0.24	0.30
Mean	0.63	0.63	1.32	1.28	0.40	0.38

^aSalicylic acid separated and estimated through silica-gel TLC using chloroform: acetic acid (9:1 vol/vol) solvent system.

^bChlorogenic and gallic acids separated on silica-gel using methanol: acetic acid: water (9:1:1 vol/vol) solvent system.

Resistance to rice gall midge (GM) in Kerala, India

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We evaluated 135 varieties against GM *Orseolia oryzae*. Damage was very severe during 1988 wet season (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov) in the nursery and in the

field and during 1989 dry season (Dec-Jan to Apr-May) in the field.

Test varieties were grown in 10-m² plots with two replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. Silvershoots in 10 randomly selected hills from each replication were counted at 30 d after transplanting.

IET10745 (C1924/RP9-4) showed high resistance, 10 lines showed moderate resistance (see table).

Resistance to rice GM in Kerala, India, 1988-89.

Line	Parentage	Score ^a		
		1988 wet season	1989 dry season	Mean
IET11070	Pusa 2-21/WGL 28171	3	2	2.5
IET11581	Rajendra/IR30	3	3	3.0
IET10745	C1924/RP9-4	0	0	0
IET10750	Asha/Kranthi	3	2	2.5
IET10726	Phalgune/Ptb 21	3	1	2.0
IET10314	IR62/Parmel	3	3	3.0
IET10847	PR106/OBS528	3	1	2.0
IET11451	Vikram/Mashin	3	2	2.5
IET11160	Ratna/ARC10659	3	3	3.0
IET11464	Ratna/ARC5984	3	2	2.5
IET11465	Ratna/ARC5984	3	1	2.5
	TN1 (susceptible check)	9	9	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = more than 25% infected tillers.

Resistance of rice to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* in free-choice and no-choice tests

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To identify resistance to planthoppers and leafhoppers, rice germplasm is commonly screened under a free-choice bulk seedling test that easily separates highly resistant and susceptible germplasm. However, the test is not completely reliable in differentiating genetic resistance from "pseudoresistance" resulting from escape or uneven distribution of insects in the seedling trays.

We compared free-choice and no-choice tests using the reactions of 28 rice varieties with known or unknown genes for GLH resistance. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Seeds were sown in 70- × 50- × 10-cm wooden trays in 12-cm-long rows with 6 cm spacing between rows. Each tray had three strips of rows. Seedlings were thinned at 7 d to 15/row and infested with 3d-instar nymphs. Each tray represented a replication.

The free-choice test involved two approaches. In one, seedlings in each tray were infested by tapping GLH nymph-infested TN1 plants so that each seedling tray received about 5 nymphs/seedling. Infested seedlings were kept uncovered. In the second approach, each seedling tray was covered with a 70- × 50- × 70-cm nylon mesh cage. A precise number of 3d instars (5 nymphs/seedling) were introduced using a glass-blowing tube.

In test one, nymphs could move to different varieties in the tray and could move out of the tray. In test two, nymphs were forced to choose among the varieties within the enclosed tray.

Nymphs were counted at 1 and 3 d after infestation (DAI) and damage was recorded at 10 d on a row basis. TN1 was completely killed after DAI.

In the no-choice test, 10 pregerminated seeds/row were sown for each variety. At 7 d, each row was covered with a 13- × 4- × 27-cm rectangular